

HOMONYMS AS A PHENOMENON ARE ONE OF THE SOURCES OF THE WORD PLAY

(BASED ON MATERIALS OF KARAKALPAK FOLKLORE)

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***Abstract:** This paper focuses on the analysis of anecdotal as one of the categories of word play and its manifestation in jokes in the Karakalpak language. The data of this research are all jokes and anecdotes which were collected from different books and Karakalpak folklore. The pun, also called paronomasia, is a form of wordplay which suggests two or more meanings, by exploiting multiple meanings of words or of similar-sounding words, for an intended humorous or rhetorical effect. A pun is a joke based on the interplay of homonyms — words with the same form but different meanings. It can also play with words that sound similar but not exactly the same. The joke's humor comes from the confusion of the two meanings. It should be noted that homonymy is one of the key techniques for creating linguistic jokes, which makes it an integral attribute of intercultural communication. In this article, we will consider the question of homonyms of the language game in the modern Karakalpak language. Language games have deep roots in the Karakalpak language. In this article, we have found the Karakalpak folklore. In our linguistics, such questions have not yet been investigated. Therefore, we want to establish a base of such directions. In Karakalpak folklore, two volumes are devoted to anecdotes. This means that the Karakalpak language has a large fundamental homonymous resource of the language games.*

***Keywords:** word play, homonyms, Karakalpak language, Karakalpak folklore, anecdote.*

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study is primarily due to this paradoxical discrepancy between the level of popularity of a pun and the level of knowledge about it. Moreover, the features of semantics, poetics, stylistics, multi-level language/speech means and mechanisms of formation of the Karakalpak pun are of primary scientific interest since the techniques of pun convergence of words are not only organically included in the general system of satirical style of many Karakalpak writers, but also reflect our national mentality.

Nowadays, homonyms are very common, and it has become embedded in our daily life, art, and even in culture. Homonyms are often found in poetry, humorous stories, and anecdotes.

Homonyms, used in speech, serve as one of the ways to create a comic effect. The comic effect, based on homonymous words, is based on a ridiculous substitution, words that have a similar form, but the content plan will be different.

Currently, the problem of studying homonyms is becoming more and more difficult.

It is in demand in connection with the study of such tasks as ways to create a comic in an anecdote. The popularity of homonyms as a language game technique attracts the attention of many modern scientists.

Many scientists have investigated this phenomenon, such as R Aldington, Partington, K. Fischer, Henri Bergson, Walter Redfern, Boldareva E, Volkova E, Petrenko M, Kurganova E, Kurganov E, Sereda P, Sannikov V. Z, Salnikova T, Toropova O, Amiri L, Muratbay Nizanov and many others.

Linguists who use the terms "word play", "pun" proceed from lexical (if homonyms are played) levels. At the same time, the possibility of playing a higher level language unit is not denied. Thus, I.R. Galperin in the definition of pun puts in one row the playing of meanings of both a word or a phrase ("of a word or phrase"). (Galperin, 1958).

The pun is a witticism which relies on its effect on playing with the different meanings of a word, or bringing two words together with the similar form but different meanings; it is also called paronomasia (Crystal, 2003). Razzak et al. define a pun as the use of the same word (or two words similar in sound) in different senses for humorous purposes (Razzak et al, 1981).

It should be noted that homonymy, after all, is one of the most productive lexical phenomena of the language, which helps the language to show its gaming potential. At the same time, the main function of this phenomenon can be noted as a language game, which is used by the speaker to entertain himself and the interlocutor, to intrigue him, to make him listen. The joke allows you to express strange and even absurd thoughts (Salnikova, 2010).

Despite the fact that many researchers note the fact that communication is difficult due to the use of homonyms in speech, it is impossible not to pay attention to the fact that homonyms often aesthetically saturate it, which is especially convincingly demonstrated in the anecdote (Alexandrova, 2012).

Anecdote is one of the phenomena in which homonyms are often used, they support the traditional culture that presents us with national communicative behavior in various countries around the world.

The anecdote reflects the mentality of the people, their cultural values, vision and perception of the world, so understanding any anecdote requires knowledge of a linguistic, metalinguistic and psycholinguistic nature (Tarasenko, 2009).

Anecdotes based on homonymy are one of the most concise and interesting ones. E. Kurganov notes that it is the space of anecdote that gives homonymy a new life, showing its creative character (Sereda, 2013).

Homonymy is used in the anecdote with maximum intensity and high efficiency. Moreover, very often it is homonymy that allows the anecdote to maximally aestheticize the communicative act (Salnikova, 2010).

The main use of homonyms is anecdote, where they are used to create a comic effect. Comics is realized by a double understanding of the language utterance. First, one masking understanding of a situation or language expression comes to mind, and then it is indicated that another possible understanding is meant. The disguised understanding becomes apparent to the addressee of the speech only as a result of a sudden guess or insight. The suddenness of a guess or insight is important: a disguised understanding should not become apparent before time.

Homonyms are a special type of vocabulary of the Karakalpak language. Due to the fact that they are words with different meanings, have a similar external form, this largely determines their widespread use as a special stylistic means.

The vast range of possibilities of the word play is represented by the fact that homonymic units are related to each other only in sound and writing, but not in semantics, and therefore the joint use of homonyms in the text is unexpected for the reader and listener.

METHOD

The development of problems related to the category of homonymy as a mechanism for creating a language game is relevant since one of the main directions of linguistics is the study of the relationship and interaction of the form and content of a word against the background of the broader problem of violation of the "law of the sign" in the natural human language.

Homonyms are studied from various points of view – formal, semantic, etymological, word-formation, functional, normative, stylistic and psycholinguistic – and on different language material.

Homonyms and the flexible use of different meanings of words create an interesting stylistic effect that enriches our lives. The deliberate use and collision of homonymous words has always been and is an indispensable means of witty play. This is done to give the product expressiveness and expression of speech.

A pun is a stylistic turn, a play on words based on the comic playing of consonant words or phrases with incompatible meanings. Puns are based on polysemy, homonymy, homographs, comic etymology of words, etc. Puns are also based on the stylistic use of different meanings of the same word.

The main method is direct observation of semantic, phonetic and stylistic features of a pun, their description; observation of lexical, phraseological and other means of forming an expressive-speech structure of a pun and description of their types. The analysis of scientific and theoretical sources, the comparative-comparative method is used when considering the differential features of language means of creating a pun, as well as methods of contextual and semantic-stylistic analysis. To identify and clarify the properties of a pun and its constituent units, techniques, comparisons, transformations, inversions, and synonymous substitution are used.

Puns often rely on homonyms for their effects. The aesthetic impact of puns, in particular, requires that the audience make a temporary, but perceptible, misinterpretation of a sentence. The research of some linguists indicates that the likelihood of misinterpretation will be greater with some class homonyms, and so these homonyms should be used more than different class homonyms in puns. Furthermore, the rated quality of some class homonyms should be higher than that for different class homonyms. More generally, whereas prior studies have treated homonyms equivalently in analysis and experimentation, our understanding of these words and how they are processed could be enriched by studying homonym subclasses that might differ on various dimensions such as lexical organization, language evolution, and word play.

In this article, we analyze the Karakalpak folklore. Because when it comes to anecdote, we understand this folklore. Karakalpak folklore consists of more than 100 volumes and the 85th volume is called anecdotes. First, we will read this volume and homonyms. Then we choose anecdotes that made up two or more homonyms. And then we will discuss such anecdotes and word plays.

We can trace the use of the literalization technique, which is implemented with the help of a communication participant who understands a stable expression literally and gives an appropriate response. Moreover, by playing homonymous words, a non-standard situation is created.

It should be noted that the use of such a word play technique as homonymy is becoming an increasingly popular trend at the present time. This is because this technique is an effective way to create a witty and unexpected joke. The main

function of homonymy should be called the creation of a two-fold situation, implemented by playing with words.

Also, in this article, we have considered one of the most popular techniques used in anecdote to create a comic effect, homonymy. Despite the ambiguity of scientists' understanding of this phenomenon, it should be recognized that homonymy is a technique of word play, which cannot only act as a hindrance that distorts the understanding of the utterance, but also one of the most productive lexical phenomena of the language, which not only helps the language to show its gaming potential, but also performs many positive functions in the process of communication.

So, the technique of combining different forms is especially often used in poetic puns. In them, such a collision also performs different functions. For example, it can be used for educational and explanatory purposes.

The love of homonymy is a characteristic feature of the Karakalpak anecdote. We claim that the Karakalpak language, which contains many homonyms and expressions, is an ideal material for creating puns.

As mentioned above, a special role in the construction of jokes is played by the use of anecdote homonyms. We are based on Karakalpak folklore when creating word plays.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pun is a form of wordplay usually defined as a deliberate communicative strategy, or the result thereof, used with a specific semantic or pragmatic effect in mind. Wordplay itself is the general name for various textual strategies in which authors exploit the structure of a language to bring about two similar forms with similar meanings.

In jokes there is important service of much meaning, homonym words, and the repetition of sounds is emphasized in fast pronunciation. As the examples below demonstrate, homonyms are a rich source of anecdotes. Now we begin to consider the examples:

Bir jigit bir sulıw kelinshektiń úyine jumısı bolıp baradı. Kelinshek qatıbilamıq pisirip atır eken. Ol jigittiń aldına ıssı qatıbilamıqtı qoyǵan. Jigit háy-páyine qaramastan, qasıqtı toltırıp urtlaǵanda qatıbilamıq tańlayına qata qoyǵan.

- *Minaw qayjerdiń aǵashı? – degen jigit, kózinen jas aǵıp, tómen qaray almay ańqayıp shańaraqqa qarap.*

Sonda kelinshek:

- *Sazlaw jerdiń aǵashı, sabırsız jigittiń sazası, - dep, jigitti juwaptan da utıptı. (Karakalpak folklore, 394)*

Here, the anecdote is based on a homonym word **saz**.

In the following anecdote, a pun is created by using the verb-homonyms *shabıw*, *beriw*, *salıw*:

Ómirbek bir kúni joldıń boyında turǵan eken, bir topar xanniń jawshılar kele beripti. Olar Ómirbektiń janına kelip irkiledi de:

- *Yabınıń jolı qaysı? – dep soraptı.*
- *Attan túsip keliń, kórsetemen, depti Ómirbek.*

Jawshılar attan túsip, Ómirbektiń janına kelipti.

Sonda Ómirbek joldıń ortasına kelip, talayıp turıp:

- *Mınaw arbanıń digirshiginiń jolı, mınaw yabınıń jolı, - dep kórsetipti.*

Sonda jolawshılardıń onıń sózine ashıwı kelip:

- *Shabıń, úyi kúygirdiń balasın! – depti.*
- *Shappasańız da barasız, jol jaqın, - depti sonda Ómirbek.*
- *Berip jiberiń aqmaqtıń basına! – depti jawshılardıń baslıǵı gázeplenip.*
- *Berseńiz beriń, qaytarsın alarsız, - depti Ómirbek olardıń ústinen*

kúlip.

- *Salıp jiberiń ladanniń mańlayına! – dep jolawshılar Ómirbekke tura umtılıptı.*

Ómirbek olardıń ústinen kúlip:

- *Salsańız salıp jiberiń, ayrılısqan jerde alarsız, - dep juwap berip óta ketipti. (Karakalpak folklore, 395)*

Consider the following anecdote:

Ómirbekke bir jaqsı kóretuǵın dostı kelip:

- *Dostım Ómirbek, men nasibaydı **qoydım**, - depti.*

Sonda Ómirbek dostına qarap:

- *Qayerge? Dastıǵıńnıń astına ma? – depti.*

Dostı aytqanına pánt jepti. (Karakalpak folklore, 396)

Here, the verb-homonyms *qoyıw* are played, like 'put' and 'stop'.

*Ómirbek qazı bolıptı. Oǵan eki adam arız aytıp kelipti. Birewi kelgen kúni-aq qazıǵa **qırq** tilla para ótkeripti.*

*Birinshi kúni sóz **qırq** tilla para bergen adamnıń paydasına sheshilipti.*

*Ekinshi adam sol kúni tünde Ómirbekke **júz** tilla para beripti.*

*Keyingi kúni sóz **júz** tilla bergen adamnıń paydasına kóshe bergen soń:*

- *Qazımız gápti **qırqıp-qırqıp** aytpaysań ba? – depti qırq tilla bergen adam.*

Sonda Ómirbek:

- *Háy ladan, júz bar, qátere bar, - dep, isti júz tilla bergen adamniń paydasına sheshken eken.* (Karakalpak folklore, 397)

In this example, the use of homonyms makes the situation comical qırq: 'forty' and 'cut' and júz: hundred and face. It is worth noting that the use of homonyms in an anecdote has a deep meaning.

A pun not only creates a funny situation created by using the word match form, it conveys an uncomfortable situation. Consider the following examples:

Joqarıdağı gáp elge taralıp ketip, Palwaniyazdıń qızın heshkim ayttırıp kelmeytuǵın bolıptı. Bir jigit táwekel etip, qızdıń ákesi joqta sóylesip turadı eken. Gewgim túsken waqıtta palwaniyaz jumıstan qayıptı. Bir jigittiń úyinen shıqqanın kórip qalıptı da:

- *Há, bala, **nasıbayıń** bar ma? – dep dawıslaptı.*

Ol jigit albirap qalıp:

- *Aǵa, nasıbayım joq edi, - depti.*

- *Háy, naysap, - depti Palwaniyaz, - **nasıbayıń** bolmasa, biziń qızǵa kelip ne qılasań?* (Karakalpak folklore, 408)

Here, the homonyms nasıbay are used, with the meanings 'one of the types of tobacco products' and 'male sexual organ'. In the following anecdote, the homonyms neden 'how much' and 'what consists of or from what' are played out:

Bir kúni Ómirbek laqqı bazarǵa qoy satayın dep eki-úsh qoy alıp barsa, bazarda bazarshılar onnan “qoylarıń neden?” dep soray beripti.

Ómirbek laqqı olarǵa “qoylarım ot penen júnnen” dep juwap beripti. Eń aqırında Ómirbek qoyların sata almay, úyine qayıtıp alıp ketipti. Qoyların satalmaǵanın kórgen Ómirbektiń hayalı oǵan:

- *Sen barıp turǵan tirsekseń, jurt qusap sóylegenińde, sen de qoylarıńdı satqan bolar ediń, - depti.*

Sonda Ómirbek hayalına:

- *Men tirsek emespen, búgingi bazardağı adamlardıń ózleri tirsek eken, bolmasa nege “Qoylarıń neden?” dep soray beredi, - depti.* (Karakalpak folklore, 448)

Here are the following examples:

Ómirbek bazarǵa barıp kóp aralap júripti. Eń keyininde miywa bazarına barıp, alma satıp turǵan bir adamnan:

- *Mınaw satıp turǵanıń ne? – dep soraptı.*

- *Alma, - depti ol.*

- *Alǵanda ne qılasań, - dep eń úlken birewin alıp jepti.* (Karakalpak

folklore, 467)

In this anecdote, he plays on the homonyms of alma 'apple' and 'don't take it'. The misunderstanding that occurred between the seller and the visitor of the bazaar creates a comic effect. Let's offer another anecdote:

Ómirbek bir awıldan qıdırıp kiyatırsa, aldınan bir jolawshı shıǵıp:

- *Inim Túyemoyınǵa qalay shıǵaman? – dep soraptı.*

Sonda Ómirbek:

- *Artqı jaǵınan minip, órkeshtiń ústi menen tuwrı shıǵasań, aǵa, - depti.*

(Karakalpak folklore, 474)

Here a comic situation occurred with a camel. Consider the following example:

Palwaniyaz awıllası Ismamut penen birge Nókiske jıynalısqı barıptı. Qaytarsın qızın kórip keteyin dep meduchilishege barsa, qızı sırtta júrgen eken.

- *He, qızım, sabaq joq pa? – depti Palwaniyaz.*

- *Barǵo, dene tárbiyası sabaǵı. Muǵallım “formań joq” dep shıǵarıp jiberdi.*

- *Qáne, arman qara, - depti Palwaniyaz qızına, - endi berman qara. Muǵallımın poqqını jepti, gúlli forma sende tur ǵoy, qızım!.* (Karakalpak folklore, 411)

The similar forms of forma 'uniforms and forma 'figure' are the key points of forming the pun.

The leading role in forming puns is played by structured words. The basis of the word play is the mental operation of segmentation of the word into its components. Ambiguity leads to the fact that each time as a result of disassembly, assembling and analysis in the output one or another meaning is obtained.

The word play performs an entertaining function since in this anecdote, the above-mentioned function is due to a misunderstanding by one interlocutor of the other.

The word play performs many functions not only in the process of communication, but also in creating a joke, which gives it a special meaning and fills it with meaning. Moreover, we have analyzed the techniques that give the word play the ability to implement functions. Each of the techniques gives the anecdote a special semantic content and a comic effect.

Homonyms are played in puns and anecdotes where just a play on words is needed. In other cases, homonyms are only a hindrance to understanding, which is convincingly refuted by the explanatory dictionaries of the modern Karakalpak language, which contain the frequencies of several of the most common words.

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that homonyms are indeed a widespread method of creating a word play in Karakalpak anecdotes. It

should be noted that in the course of our research, the hypothesis that homonyms are an ideal tool for word play, not only for playing with words and achieving the effect of surprise for the listener, but also an excellent tool for witty and ironic ridiculing of human vices and stereotypes existing in people, is being tested.

During the analysis, we analyzed 300 anecdotes, but we selected 9 of the most colorful, bright and correct anecdotes. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that Omirbek and Palwaniyaz are the main image of the word play in Karakalpak anecdotes.

Moreover, we have analyzed the functions that the word play performs in Karakalpak anecdotes. Among the many functions performed by the word play created on the basis of homonymy, we have identified the following functions: comic, entertaining and ridiculing.

Therefore, summarizing all of the above, we can conclude that the functions that the word play performs in the anecdote do not exist by themselves, but are carried out with the help of various linguistic and pragmatic techniques that help to get the desired effect.

In general communicative language, the homonyms have their own nuance, used especially in word play. And in some cases, the use of such wordplay leads the reader to understand the tragedy of the situation. Professionals can use the possibilities of homonyms to create a wordplay that becomes a source of expression of professional units.

Homonyms help the writer create a comical situation. Homonyms are used to create puns. A pun is a stylistic figure based on the humorous use of polysemous words and homonyms.

Ana jerde eki zalım bar.
Úyde otır kútip kobra.

The considered examples prove that the main functions of homonyms are to give the content a great expression, highlight any phenomena and strengthen their meaning for creating puns and building rhymes.

We will conclude by mentioning one implication of this work for another aspect of language use, namely linguistic humor. Puns and other jokes often rely on homonyms for their effects. The aesthetic impact of puns, in particular, requires that the audience make a temporary, but perceptible, misinterpretation of a sentence. The research of some linguists indicates that the likelihood of misinterpretation will be greater with the same homonyms, and so these homonyms should be used more than different class homonyms in puns. Furthermore, the rated quality of the same

homonyms should be higher than that for different class homonyms. More generally, whereas prior studies have treated homonyms equivalently in analysis and experimentation, our understanding of these words and how they are processed could be enriched by studying homonym subclasses that might differ on various dimensions such as lexical organization, language evolution, and word play.

CONCLUSION

In this article, we looked at the role of homonyms in the word play. To begin with, we considered the concept of the game itself. A game is defined as an action that takes place within certain time limits according to voluntarily accepted rules, and this action often causes laughter. A particular type of game that manifests itself in speech activity is a word play.

We also consecrated such a question as the study of anecdote. And anecdote is a form of laughing text that has a number of properties inherent in the laughing culture. First, one of the main functions of the anecdote is to parody all the manifestations of modern culture, that is, to deliberately reduce its norms, values, and ideals, and to present the realities in an absurd, absurd way. Secondly, the laughter of an anecdote is also directed at everything and everyone, it is universal, does not exclude any phenomena of reality, including the laughing themselves. Third, the anecdote is theatrical, like many phenomena of the laughing culture.

Moreover, since one of our tasks is to analyze the implementation of homonymy as a source of word play in the Karakalpak anecdote, we could not but consider in detail such a lexical device of the language as homonymy. The main field of use of homonyms is anecdote, in which this phenomenon fully manifests its gaming potential. In general, in word plays, the culmination can be addressed to homonyms and context.

References:

1. Alexandrova E. M. (2012) Homonymy in intercultural communication: problems of classification [Electronic resource]. p 12 URL: <https://docviewer.yandex.ru/?>
2. Karakalpak folklore. (2014) Editor-in-Chief : Nagmet Aimbetov, Responsible Editors: A.Alniyazov, J. Khoshniyazov. Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Department of Karakalpakstan, Karakalpak Scientific-Research Institute of Humanitarian Sciences. Nukus, Ilim, Volume 77-87.
3. Kaljanov Ali. (2023). Grammatical homonyms in modern Karakalpak language. The International Journal of Language and Cultural (TIJOLAC) 5 (1), 26-31
4. Kaljanov Ali (2022). Homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language: general theoretical questions. Science and Education 3 (1), 368-385
5. Kaljanov Ali. (2022). Features of the Study of the Degree of Homonyms in Karakalpak Language. Neo Scientific Peer Reviewed Journal, 4, 23–34. Retrieved from <https://www.neojournals.com/index.php/nspj/article/view/28>

6. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The Universal (Mixed) Homonyms in Modern Karakalpak Language. *Science and Education*, 1 (5), 142-145.
7. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Grammatical homonyms in modern Karakalpak language. *Journal on International Social Science*, 1 (1), 1-6.
8. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Problems of training homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language. *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education*, 1(2), 10-13.
9. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The Some Questions of Grammatical Homonyms in Modern Karakalpak Language. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 2 (9), 19-21.
10. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). The essence of homonyms in the Karakalpak language. *Journal of Foreign Languages and Linguistics*. 2 (3), 24-26.
11. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). The short study of multiple homonyms in Karakalpak language. *International scientific and current research conferences*, 51-53.
12. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Problematic aspects of grammatical homonyms. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11 (6), 815-821.
13. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Theoretical basis of homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language. *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*, 36-40.
14. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Межъязыковые омонимы в русском и каракалпакском языках. *Современная филология: проблемы и перспективы*, 225-229.
15. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Qaraqalpaq tilindegi omonimler klassifikatsiyasınıń ayırım máseleleri. *Вестник Каракалпакского отделения Академии наук Республики Узбекистан*, 265 (4), 196-199.
16. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). On the state of the problem of homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language. *Вестник КГУ им. Бердаха*, 52 (3), 182-185.
17. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Til oqıtıwda omonimlerdiń ayırım ózgeshelikleri. «Түркий филологияның әхмийетли мәселелери». *Илимий мақалалар топламы*, 190-193.
18. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Single homonyms in Karakalpak language. “Қиёсий адабиётшунослик, чоғиштира тилшунослик ва таржимашунослик: муаммо, ечим ва истикболлар” мавзуйдаги халқаро конференция, 74-76.
19. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Omonimlerdi ajratıwda konteksttiń áhmiyeti. *Uluslararası Türkbilim Öğrenci Kurultayı Bildiriler Kitabı*, 194-200.
20. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). From the point of view of the phenomenon of homonyms in the Karakalpak language. *Yangi O'zbekistonda ilm-fan va ta'lim*, 1 (1), 182-184.
21. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Lexico-grammatical homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language. *Science and Education*, 2 (11), 992-1001.
22. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). The homonymous resources of the word play in the modern Karakalpak language (based on materials of Karakalpak folklore). *International journal of word art*, 4 (3), 212-218.
23. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). The short analysis of homonyms in the Karakalpak language. "Noi tendințe în predarea limbajelor de specialitate în contextul racordării învățământului la cerințele pieței muncii", *conferință internațională online*. 4, 251-255.
24. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). A short step towards the classification of homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language. *Electronic journal of actual problems of modern science, education and training*, 12, 41-45.
25. Kaljanov Ali. (2021). Linguistic features of the sources of homonyms in the modern Karakalpak language. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 17 (2), 123-126.
26. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Роль межъязыковых омонимов в преподавании языка (на примере русского и каракалпакского языков). *Advanced methods of teaching foreign languages and their implementation issues in the system of training security personnel*, 276-278.

27. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Ibrayim Yusupov shigarmalarında omonimlarning qollanilish o'zgarishlari. "Uzbek language development and problems of international cooperation": materials of international scientific-practical conference, 318-321.
28. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Некоторые межъязыковые омонимы в русском и каракалпакском языке. «SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS» Scientific Journal, 1 (1), 46-51.
29. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The some interlingual homonyms in modern Karakalpak language. UzAcademia Scientific-methodical journal, 1 (2), 206-210.
30. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Вопрос омонимии в преподавании языка. Современная психология и педагогика: проблемы, анализ и результаты, 4, 511-515.
31. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Qoraqalpoq tilidagi omonimlarga bir nazar. Ta'limga kompetensiyaviy yondashuv: muammo va yechimlar" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy onlayn konferensiya materiallari, 30-32.
32. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). A few words about homonyms. Republican scientific-practical online conference "Application of modern methods in the development of science. 228-230.
33. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Question of homonyms in teaching language. Чет тилларни ўқитишда инновацион усуллардан фойдаланишнинг аҳамияти ва таржимашунослик муаммолари" mavzusidagi I xalqaro onlayn ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari, 61-62.
34. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The question of translation homonyms. Filologiya masalalari" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy onlayn konferensiya materiallari, 91-93.
35. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The features of grammatical homonyms in Karakalpak language. Digital technologies in modern education, current trends and development factors in philology and pedagogy, 191-193.
36. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). 現代カラカルパク語における同音異義語. Intercultural communication through the prism of tourism in Uzbekistan: Experience, current issues and perspectives, 104-105.
37. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Galaba xabar qurallarında omonimlarning qollanilish o'zgarishlari (reklama misolında). Глобалласуу процесинде галаба хабар куралларының роли. Халықаралық илимий конференция мақалалары топламы, 163-165.
38. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The question of translation homonyms via speech identification and dictionary use. Ўзбекистон илмий-амалий тадқиқотларда талабаларнинг ўрни: мақолалар тўплами, (5), 75-86.
39. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Til ilimindeki omonimlarga qisqasha tushinik. Материалы Республиканской научно-практической конференции «Наука и инновации в современных условиях Узбекистана», (2), 128.
40. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Interlingual homonyms in English and Karakalpak language. Materials of the XVII International scientific and practical Conference Cutting-edge science, 10 (17), 141-143.
41. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Interlingual homonyms in the Karakalpak and Japanese language. Nutq madaniyati va o'zbek tilshunosligining dolzarb muammolari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari, 158-160.
42. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Frequency of homonym meanings. Materials of the republican 15-multidisciplinary online distance conference on "Scientific and practical research in Uzbekistan", 3 (15), 45-46.
43. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). The questions of homonyms in Karakalpak language. Prospects of Development of Science and Education" Conference Proceedings, 1 (4), 425-433.
44. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Homonyms in translations. Prospects of Development of Science and Education" Conference Proceedings, 1 (4), 301-304.
45. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Qaraqalpaq ham yapon tillerindeki omonimlarning qisqasha salistirma izertlenishi. "O'zbekistonda ilm-fan va ta'lim", 2 (4), 168-171.

46. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Qaraqalpaq tilindegi omonimlerdiń izertleniw máselesi hám aktuallığı. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference entitled «Urgent Problems of Philology and Teaching Foreign Languages», 184-187.
47. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Qaraqalpaq hám yapon tillerindegi tiller aralıq omonimler sıpatlaması. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference entitled «Urgent Problems of Philology and Teaching Foreign Languages», 181-184.
48. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Omonimler semantikalıq qubılıs sıpatında. Қарақалпақ филологиясының мәселелери. Илимий семинар материаллары. II Тоғлам, 195-198.
49. Kaljanov Ali. (2020). Актуальные задачи исследования вопросов омонимы в современном каракалпакском языке. International journal of word art, 3 (3), 679-683.
50. Salnikova T. V. (2010) Homonymy in anecdotes in the mirror of the language game [Electronic resource]. p 33,45 URL: <http://goo.gl/HUyDFf>
51. Sereda P. V. (2013) Homonymy and polysemy as a tool of the language game [Electronic resource]. p 23. URL: <http://goo.gl/MWI3tr>
52. Galperin I.R. (1958). Essays on stylistics of the English language. № 4. SILT, p. 460-465.
53. Crystal, D. (2003). A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics. 5th ed. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Ltd, p 467
54. Razzaq, F. A. and Helen Al-Hassan. (1981). The college composition. Baghdad, Iraq: The Institute for the Development of English Language Teaching in Iraq, p 123.
55. T.Tarasenko. (2009) Anecdote and translation [Text] / T. V. Tarasenko // Bulletin of IGLU-IGLU, , p- 124.